

AVOID TECHNICAL PROBLEMS IN LV NETWORKS : FROM DATA-DRIVEN MONITORING TO PREDICTIVE CONTROL

Micael SIMÕES INESC TEC- Portugal micael.f.simoes@inesctec.pt	Gil SAMPAIO INESC TEC-Portugal gss@inesctec.pt	André MADUREIRA INESC TEC-Portugal andre.g.madureira@inesctec.pt	Ricardo BESSA INESC TEC- Portugal rbessa@inesctec.pt	Jorge PEREIRA INESC TEC-Portugal jpereira@inesctec.pt
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Diogo LOPES EDP Distribuição - Portugal diogo.lopez@edp.pt	David FONSECA EDP Distribuição - Portugal david.fonseca@edp.pt
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Pedro GODINHO MATOS EDP Distribuição – Portugal pedro.godinhomatos@edp.pt	Rita PIRES EDP Distribuição – Portugal rita.pires@edp.pt
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ABSTRACT

In order to avoid voltage problems induced by the connection of large amounts of renewable-based energy generation to distribution networks, new advanced tools that are able to exploit the benefits of Distributed Energy Resources (DER) need to be developed. This paper describes the approach taken in InteGrid project to perform the active management of Low Voltage (LV) Networks, with low levels of observability, exploiting the flexibility provided by Distribution System Operator's (DSO) resources, and private consumers through their Home Energy Management Systems (HEMS). The proposed approach defends preventive management of the LV network, resorting to forecasts of microgeneration and load to estimate the network's state for future instants.

INTRODUCTION

InteGrid project aims to demonstrate the feasibility of smart distribution networks, coping with a high amount of renewable energy sources (RESs), and making use of the available DERs flexibility for various functions / business cases at different levels. At the LV level, the project is developing and demonstrating a LV state estimation (LVSE) and a LV control (LVC) tools, making use of smart meter data and a complementarity of multiple technologies, offering different types, degrees and levels of flexibility, such as demand response at domestic level and energy storage (at a utility scale or domestic scale).

Background

To address these challenges, the InteGrid Portuguese demonstrator will implement an Advanced Distribution Management Systems (ADMS) integrated with third party systems of EDP Distribuição (GIS, SYSGRID), and incorporate the tools developed by INESC TEC.

The interoperability of the ADMS will be ensured by near-real-time and historical measurements as well as by the available flexibilities, allowing producing forecasts and setting control strategies to solve foreseen network problems. A Grid-Market Hub (trading platform) provides the interface between the different actors. Figure 1 shows the general architecture of this solution.

Figure 1: InteGrid Solution Architecture

InteGrid's Solution

Typically, and unlike HV and even MV systems, LV distribution systems do not have significant real-time metering to monitor the operation of the networks. This lack of observability means that there are no real-time measurements of all (or even most) network nodes, nor it is known the connection phase of each customer. On the other hand, the flexibility of specific resources, such as storage devices that are available in LV distribution networks, may be an important resource for DSOs to manage their networks. This can be especially useful to avoid the occurrence of technical violations, such as line/transformer congestions or poor voltage profiles, which are often a consequence of the integration of large amounts of renewable-based distributed generation.

Concerning the monitoring and control of LV networks, InteGrid's solution aims to exploit flexibility from different sources, either provided by individual domestic clients that can adjust their consumption level, or by assets that may be owned by the DSO. These flexibilities can be used to provide some form of ancillary services to support the operation of the distribution system.

The project proposes to address this by developing a set of tools specifically designed for LV distribution systems that can increase the capability of monitoring the existing assets and operating conditions as well as of controlling specific flexible resources. The proposed tools include a State Estimation tool together with a Low Voltage control tool for LV networks.

The proposed approach does not rely on heavy

computational models, such as the ones used in traditional DMS applications, but rather exploit data-driven processes for network monitoring that can provide good solutions in a reasonable amount of time. Moreover, by exploiting forecasting applications, both for demand and for renewable-based generation (such as PV systems), the proposed solution uses a predictive control approach to identify technical problems that may arise during operation, and hence propose mitigation actions.

DISTRIBUTED MONITORING AND CONTROL OF LV NETWORKS

As previously mentioned, the proposed control approach encompasses two core tools: the LVSE and the LVC. The LVSE provides a full snapshot of the LV network operating conditions (including a probabilistic characterization of the electrical measurements) and it is used to generate voltage alarms that trigger the LVC module. In fact, both tools were designed so they can be locally installed in the Distribution Transformer Controller (DTC) at the secondary substation, and provide a semi-autonomous control of the LV grid. For instance, the distribution operator can define which kind of alarms generated by the LVSE, or control actions determined by the LVC, require its notification and/or validation.

The LVSE uses historical information gathered by the smart grid infrastructure along with some real-time measurements and exogenous information, like weather forecasts and calendar information (hour of the day, day of the week, etc.). In preventive mode, a few hours ahead, the LVC uses net load and PV energy forecasts as input to define a set of preventive control actions that help keeping voltage within admissible upper and lower limits. Figure 2 depicts this preventive control.

Figure 2: Monitoring and preventive control strategy for LV networks

LV State Estimation (LVSE) Tool

The LVSE is a data-driven state estimator based exclusively on historical data and on a small subset of smart meters with real-time communication of active power and voltage magnitude measurements, bringing the following innovations:

- Uses a very limited number of real-time metering points (assuming that smart meter measurements are sent every 24 hours or every week).
- The output takes the form of quantiles representing uncertainty in the state estimation process. This enables the creation of probabilistic

alarms for voltage problems, e.g. 95% probability of overvoltage in a specific node.

- Neither topological information, nor electrical characteristics of the elements of the grid are necessary.
- Exogenous variables can be integrated in the state estimation process.

Fundamental concept behind the data-driven state estimation

The central principle behind the proposed LVSE is to search for analog events in the historical dataset, using a set of explanatory variables as depicted in Figure 3. The method combines measurements collected by the subset of smart meters with real-time communication and the MV/LV substation meter, together with voltage observations from the previous day and from all the meters installed in the LV grid. Exogenous variables, such as the most recent numerical weather predictions, information about demand response actions or dynamic price signals are other potential explanatory variables if available.

Figure 3: The LVSE uses the most recent measurements and historical data along with exogenous variables

Practical operation of the LVSE

Three different modes of operation were developed:

1. Real-time state estimation

As soon as new set of real-time measurements is available (e.g. every 15 or 30 minutes), the state estimator will automatically determine the most likely state of the system. The state variables are the voltage magnitudes and power injections at each phase of every node of the network. These results are stored in a database and include a probabilistic distribution of the estimations expressed by percentiles in the range 5% - 95%.

2. Update historical and tune hyper-parameters

The arrival of a new set of historical measurements (e.g. every 24 hours or week) triggers the state estimation to perform two actions: analyze the new historical data and tune hyper-parameters necessary to the estimation algorithm. Since the data may contain outliers and gaps, the state estimator provides a number of sub-function to validate data, detect outliers and fill gaps of information. Only then, the new historical data is added to the database. Additionally, this new information is used to tune hyper-parameters of the estimation algorithm, using the Nelder-Mead dynamic simplex method (DynSimplex) [1], in such

a way it adapts constantly to the consumption and generation patterns of the network.

3. Initiate hyper-parameters and perform feature selection
 Before any real-time state estimation, the algorithm should optimize its hyper-parameters according to the specific characteristics of the network. This is achieved using an EPSO [2] that aims at minimizing the estimation error. Moreover, the estimation algorithm uses a number of explanatory variables in its learning process. Depending on the variable to be estimated different weights should be given to each source of information, thus the state estimator embeds a feature selection algorithm based on Least Absolute Shrinkage and Selection Operator (LASSO) and Bayesian Optimization [3].

It should be noted that the LVSE could be used as a standalone tool to support the monitoring of the LV grid. More details about the LVSE can be found in [4].

Computational implementation and robustness

Some features of the LVSE are important to highlight, namely regarding its low computational requirements and robustness. As mentioned before, this tool was designed considering the possibility of a local deployment in a DTC, which usually offers very limited resources, both in processing and memory. In Figure 4 are represented the main elements that comprise the LVSE tool:

- A folder that receives the most recent historical data gathered by the smart meters, and the network file that indicates the type of meters in the network and contains the real-time measurements available. The first arrives every 24 hours, for example, and will trigger the second operation mode aforementioned. The later will arrive every 30 minutes and trigger the first mode.
- A SQLite database to store historical data, estimation results, and configuration parameters.
- A REST API that enables the communication between the client and the service.
- The LVSE executable file.

Figure 4: Elements of the LVSE tool

Despite the use of very lightweight components, the LVSE optimizes the use of memory by selecting the amount of historical data necessary to run. This feature is intrinsic to the estimation algorithm itself since it gives more importance to more recent events (a thorough explanation about the data-aging selectivity can be found in [4]). Besides, the use of LASSO enables to reduce considerably

the number of explanatory variables since it indicates which quantities have significance in the estimation.

Finally, the LVSE was developed to overcome changes to the metering infrastructure. The unavailability of a given meter, whether by a malfunction detected by the validation functions or by the disconnection of the device, will not prevent the process. The LVSE will determine the state only of the valid metering points and it will use the credible information available. Even considerable changes to the topology of the network or in the consumption/generation patterns can be easily contemplated using the third mode of operation of the LVSE, accessible via REST API.

LV Control (LVC) Tool

The LVC tool, initially developed within the framework of FP7 SuSAINABLE project [5], and further developed in InteGrid [6], has the following innovations:

- Exploits forecast data to run a predictive management of the available flexible resources, including customer flexibility and DSO owned resources such as Energy Storage (ES) devices and transformers with On Load Tap Changing (OLTC) capabilities.
- Uses pre-booked flexibility from domestic clients to manage voltage deviations.
- Re-evaluates the conditions of the LV grid in real-time using the most recent data available.

Preventive Active Network Management

The tool enables an active management of the LV network's voltage profiles in a preventive manner, using forecasts for the n -hours ahead of the energy consumption, renewable generation and flexibility provided by different types of DERs present in the LV network. These DERs can be property of the DSO – such as transformers with OLTC capability and ES devices – or owned by consumers willing to participate in the operation and management of the LV network, under a contractual agreement. Private consumers willing to participate in grid operation are connected to the LV network via a HEMS. Simply put, the HEMS is responsible for the optimization of the customer's consumption and for being the interface with the Grid-Market Hub, communicating the flexibility the customer has available for the next hours, which can be used by the DSO to support grid operation and to receive the flexibility activation set-points.

The LVC tool has two main operation modes, or sub-modules: the preventive control module and the real-time control module. The preventive control module initially performs an analysis of the voltage profiles in the LV network, using forecasts of the energy consumption and production. With an unbalanced three-phase power flow algorithm, it estimates the voltage values in the LV network's nodes for each instant of the n -hours ahead. A control action plan is then defined for the available flexibilities at each instant of the n -hours ahead. The resources to control are selected according to a merit order, which prioritizes DSO-owned resources relatively to

private consumers' flexibility, with the objective of reducing the operational costs. Once a control action plan is defined, the flexibility for each period is pre-booked, thus reserving the amount of flexibility required for each node and for each period of the n -hours ahead.

The objective of the real-time control module is to assess the adequacy of the control action (previously defined by the preventive control module) to the current grid state. It uses the LVSE presented before to obtain the voltage magnitude values in the network's nodes. If the control action is no longer valid (which means the grid conditions are significantly different from the forecasts), the real-time control module updates the previously established control action plan to reflect the current grid conditions, using the flexibilities available in the network at that instant.

EXPECTED RESULTS

Monitoring of the low voltage network

Preliminary tests have been conducted to assess the capabilities of the LVSE to provide a more accurate image of the network. The 33-node LV network represented in Figure 5 was used to build a simulation environment with load data from a trial by the CER in Ireland [7] and PV generation data from the SuSustainable project [8].

The following explanatory variables were considered:

- Hour and week day.
- Irradiance (homogeneous across all PV panels).
- Real-time measurements in all phases of nodes 1, 2, 3 and 4.
- Measurement in t-24 (previous day).
- Measurement in t-168 (previous week).
- Real-time active power flow measurements in all phases of the MV/LV substation.

Figure 5: 33-node LV grid used for testing the methodology (next to each load and generator it is indicated the phase)

Snapshots of the probabilistic results obtained by the LVSE for the voltage magnitude and active power injection in a node of the network are illustrated in Figures 6 and 7, respectively. In terms of execution time, the first operation mode took on average less than 2 seconds, the second, 25 seconds, and the third, 40 minutes.

Table 1 shows the performance of the LVSE during this test and on average the estimations are very accurate, especially for voltage magnitudes, although there were periods in which the estimation error of active powers was quite high. Nevertheless, load forecasting in LV grids is a well-known challenge described in the literature.

Figure 6: Probabilistic estimation of the voltage magnitude in node 18, phase T

Figure 7: Probabilistic estimation of the active power injection in node 18, phase T

Table 1: Average and maximum deviations of voltage and active power estimations

	Voltage (V)	Active Power (W)
Average deviation	0.0622	87.931
Max deviation	8.6227	3531.13

Preventive Control

The LVC tool has been extensively tested, both through simulation and laboratory tests. In this subsection, the results obtained through simulation for the preventive control module are shown. A time-horizon of 24 hours was considered and the voltage limits were set as $\pm 5\%$ of the nominal voltage. The simulation network is based on the network depicted in Figure 5. The control variables considered for the algorithm are an MV/LV OLTC transformer, an ES connected to the secondary substation and several HEMS. The consumption and production profiles are also based on real historical, being affected by an error with the objective of simulating the error associated with forecasts.

In Figure 8 it is possible to see the nodes that present voltage violations for the considered time-horizon, according to the limits established to the LVC tool. The EN 50160 limits and limits used for the execution of the LVC algorithm are also represented. Without any voltage regulation mechanism, most of the network's nodes present voltage violations for some period. The voltage profiles for the same nodes, after the application of the preventive control LVC algorithm are shown in Figure 9. Figure 10 shows in greater detail the impact that the preventive control algorithm has in the transformer with

OLTC capability, which is of interest because it is the cheaper to actuate – and therefore should be prioritized. From Figure 10 it is possible to see that the transformer is actuated in instants where voltage violations are foreseen to occur.

Figure 8: Voltage profiles of the nodes that present voltage violations, before the application of the LVC tool.

Figure 9: Voltage profiles of the nodes that present voltage violations, after the application of the preventive LVC tool

Figure 10: Voltage profile at the transformer with OLTC capability, after the application of the preventive LVC tool.

For the peak solar production period, from 11:00 until 14:30, the voltage magnitude at the transformer is maintained at around 0.97 p.u., with the objective of addressing the generalized overvoltages registered in the LV network. The transformer is also actuated at later time periods (20:30 and 21:30), where two sudden voltage drops are foreseen to occur, rising the voltage value to address the undervoltage violations forecasted for node 32, phase S and node 33, phase T (see Figure 8).

CONCLUSIONS

Both tools presented here are being tested at the INESC TEC's Smart Grids and Electric Vehicles Laboratory, and will then be deployed in a live test environment, in a smart grids pilot operated by EDP Distribuição, during the year of 2019. The pilot is intended to demonstrate the monitoring and control capabilities shown in this paper, using the smart meter infrastructure and exploiting the flexibility provided by DSO resources and private consumers, through their HEMS.

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